

Kinetics of Oxidation of 2-Propanol with Chromium(VI) : Influence of some Metal Ions and Ligands

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Kinetics of oxidation of 2-propanol by chromic acid in presence of Mn^{II}, Ce^{III}, Fe^{II} and Co^{II} sulphates and complexing ligands such as EDTA, 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline in aqueous medium have been studied. The reaction rate constants decrease by the addition of metal ions and increase in presence of ligands.

CHROMIC acid has been used in homogeneous aqueous or acetic acid solutions for the oxidation of a variety of organic compounds such as alcohols, ethers, aldehydes, ketones, acids, hydrocarbons and aliphatic cyclic acetals. These oxidation reactions have been reviewed extensively¹. Oxidation of 2-propanol by chromic acid gives quantitative yield of acetone in acidic medium².

During the oxidation of 2-propanol with Cr^{VI} in presence of Mn^{II} in aqueous acetic acid medium, a precipitate of MnO₂ is formed and the rate is reduced to one-half of its normal value³. The rate acceleration by added Mn^{II} has been noticed in other systems⁴. The addition of Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} reduces the rate for benzaldehyde oxidation by a factor of 1/3 and 1/2 respectively⁵.

A detailed study of added complexing agents like 2,2-dipyridyl, 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, pyridine, succinic acid, adipic acid and phthalic acid for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by CrO₃ reveals an acceleration of the rate constants for the first four compounds, while the last three retard it⁶. Effect of EDTA on the chromic acid oxidation of hydrazine has also been studied⁷.

Experimental

2-Propanol (E. Merck) was dried and distilled by standard procedure (b.p. 82–83°/760 mm). Sulphuric acid (AnalaR) was used as such. Chromium(VI) oxide (CrO₃) (E. Merck) was twice recrystallised using conductivity water, and its stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ce^{III} and Co^{II} sulphates, 2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, EDTA (disodium salt) (AnalaR) were used as such.

The course of the reaction was followed by iodometric determinations of residual Cr^{VI} taking care that air-oxidation of the dissolved iodides was absent. All the reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions with higher concentration of 2-propanol over that of oxidant in aqueous system. Keeping the other experimental conditions same, the metal ions and ligands concentrations were varied. Plots of log (a-x) vs time were linear, indicating the reaction to be first order with respect to [Cr^{VI}]. The product was determined by a Shimadzu-150 uv/visible spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Effect of metal ions on the rate of oxidation of 2-propanol by chromic acid :

Effect of Mn^{II} sulphate : The added Mn^{II} sulphate retards the rate of oxidation of 2-propanol by

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF METAL SULPHATES ON OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY CrO₃

[2-Propanol]=0.5 M, [CrO₃]=0.005 M, [H₂SO₄]=0.1 M, Solvent : water, Temp. = 40 ± 0.1°

[Mn ^{II}] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[Ce ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[Fe ^{II}] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[Co ^{II}] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.0	2.50	0.0	2.50	0.0	2.50	0.0	2.60
0.5	1.66	0.2	1.78	0.5	2.37	0.5	2.76
1.0	1.60	0.6	1.58	1.0	2.20	1.0	2.53
2.0	1.50	1.0	1.44	2.0	1.90	2.0	1.50
3.0	1.32	2.0	1.38	3.0	1.74	3.0	2.73
4.0	1.28	4.0	1.34	4.0	1.46	4.0	2.66
5.0	1.22	6.0	1.29	5.0	1.34	5.0	2.80
10.0	1.88	8.0	1.26	10.0	0.47	10.0	2.76
—	—	20.0	1.08	—	—	—	—

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CrO₃. The experimental results are given in Table 1. Under the experimental conditions, the oxidised manganese was not precipitated as MnO₂. The rate constant of the reaction decreases with increasing [Mn^{II}], that is the rate of disappearance of chromic acid is decreased by Mn^{II} ions. From the plot of *k*_{obs} vs [Mn^{II}] (Fig. 1a), it is clear that the rate of oxidation decreased with increasing Mn^{II} ion concentration, but the effect is more pronounced

Fig. 1

at very low [Mn^{II}]. The retardation of the reaction can be explained by the disproportionation of Cr^{IV} and Cr^V to Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III}, catalysed by Mn^{II}. The oxidation of 2-propanol with Cr^{VI} may be represented as

Mn^{III} formed in step (3) being an unstable species, is likely to be used by the substrate and converted to Mn^{II}.

In the absence of any added Mn^{II}, partial regeneration of Cr^{VI} occurs (step 4) from the reduced Cr^{IV} species. But added Mn^{II} fixes the Cr^{IV} species as Cr^{III} and thus reduces the concentration of regenerated Cr^{VI}. Thus the total concentration of Cr^{VI} available in a given time is lowered by the addition of Mn^{II} and hence the observed deceleration with increasing addition of Mn^{II} ion. This view is further supported by similar explanation offered to uphold the rate retardation by added Mn^{II} ion in the oxidation of isopropanol itself⁹ and of formic acid¹⁰.

Effect of Ce^{III} sulphate: The effect of added Ce^{III} is similar to that of Mn^{II} ion. The observed rate constants are given in Table 1. In general, the rates are retarded by increasing the concentration of Ce^{III} ion, the effect is more pronounced at very low [Ce^{III}] and reaches a limiting value at higher [Ce^{III}], which is clearly shown in the plot of *k*_{obs} vs [Ce^{III}] (Fig. 1b).

When Ce^{III} is added, initial rapid production of Ce^{IV} has been observed spectrophotometrically¹¹; the Ce^{IV} then remains at the level of the total cerium ion concentration until well after ten half-lives for chromic acid oxidation have passed. The general scheme for the effect of Ce^{III} ion may be as follows:

According to this scheme Cr^{VI} is the only oxidant reacting with the 2-propanol, while the added Ce^{III} acts as a catalyst for effective disproportionation of intermediate species, Cr^{IV} and Cr^V into Cr^{VI}, and decreases the rate constant. At high [Ce^{III}], the Ce^{IV} produced acts as an oxidant for 2-propanol.

Effect of Fe^{II} sulphate: The observed rate constants decreased on the addition of Fe^{II} sulphate. The results are given in Table 1. The plot of *k*_{obs} vs [Fe^{II}] is shown in Fig. 1c. This retardation of the rate constant is similar to that by Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} sulphates, but the extent of this effect here is different. The decrease in rate constants with increasing [Fe^{II}] may be explained with the reactions,

In the above scheme, the Fe^{III} ion, produced by steps (2), (3) and (4), favours the equilibrium shift of equation (2) towards left, which corresponds to maintaining a higher [Cr^{VI}]. The rate gets retarded as more and more of Fe^{II} is added.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF COMPLEXING LIGANDS ON OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY CrO_3

 [2-Propanol] = 0.5 M, $[\text{CrO}_3]$ = 0.005 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 0.1 M, Solvent : water, Temp. = $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$

[EDTA] $\times 10^4$ M	k_{obs} $\times 10^4$ s $^{-1}$	[2,2-Dipy] $\times 10^4$ M	k_{obs} $\times 10^4$ s $^{-1}$	[1,10-Phen] $\times 10^4$ M	k_{obs} $\times 10^4$ s $^{-1}$
0.0	2.56	0.0	2.55	0.0	2.55
0.5	2.96	0.5	2.74	0.5	2.96
1.0	3.33	1.0	3.26	1.0	3.18
2.0	3.75	2.0	3.19	2.0	3.45
3.0	4.76	3.0	4.66	3.0	3.75
4.0	5.86	4.0	5.73	4.0	4.58
5.0	6.83	5.0	6.14	5.0	4.90
10.0	7.11	10.0	11.77	10.0	8.79
15.0	7.68	—	—	—	—
20.0	8.59	—	—	—	—

Effect of Co^{II} sulphate : The experimental conditions were similar to those with Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} and Ce^{III} sulphates except that the $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}]$ ion was varied

from 5×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-3} M. The observed rate constants are given in Table 1. From the values of rate constants, it is clear that the added Co^{II} sulphate has no effect on the rate of oxidation of 2-propanol by CrO_3 under this condition. A slight variation in the observed rate constants may be attributed to the salt-effect of Co^{II} sulphate.

During the oxidation of 2-propanol, the intermediates Cr^{V} and Cr^{IV} species are formed. If the rates are low or high, these oxidation states are stabilised by Co^{II} ions but in the present investigation (Table 1) no effect on the rate of oxidation of 2-propanol was observed which clearly indicates that the intermediate species of chromium may be stabilised by the oxidation of 2-propanol only.

Effect of complexing ligands :

Effect of EDTA (disodium salt) : The kinetics of oxidation of 2-propanol by chromic acid in presence of EDTA ligand has been studied. The observed rate constants (Table 2) increase with increasing [EDTA]. From the correlation plot of k_{obs} vs [EDTA] (Fig. 2a), it is observed that at lower [EDTA], the rate constants are linear. The final product shows a violet colour which when analysed spectrophotometrically was found to contain two peaks (λ_{max} 390–395 and 550–555 nm).

Brintzinger *et al.*¹⁸ first prepared the violet Cr^{III} -EDTA complex and found that the colour of the reaction mixture depends on pH. The λ_{max} values were reported¹⁸ to be 370–390 and 550–560 nm for the Cr^{III} -EDTA complex¹⁸, the absorbance being negligible for all other materials present. These results are in good agreement with the present work.

The mechanism for the oxidation of 2-propanol with Cr^{VI} in the presence of EDTA may be represented as

Fig. 2

Thus by analogy, the acceleration of rate of oxidation of 2-propanol by EDTA can be explained by the formation of the stable complex with Cr^{III} ions, which would favour the decrease of Cr^{VI} . The formation of Cr^{III} , EDTA violet coloured complex has been confirmed by absorption spectra.

Effect of 2,2'-dipyridyl: The effect of added 2,2-dipyridyl on the oxidation of 2-propanol has been studied. The rate constants (Table 2) increased with the increase of 2,2'-dipyridyl. This acceleration is dependent linearly on the added [dipyl] (Fig. 2b). Further, the absorption spectra of the final product of oxidation of 2-propanol with Cr^{VI} in presence of 2,2'-dipyridyl gives a peak at 535 nm. The λ_{max} 530 nm for the final product of chromic acid oxidation of benzaldehyde in presence of 2,2'-dipyridyl for [diaquobis- Cr^{III} L] complex (L=2,2'-dipyridyl) has been reported⁶. Thus the oxidation process of Cr^{VI} follows the sequence: $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{IV}} \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$. Cr^{II} may get oxidised to Cr^{III} by atmospheric air or by the solvent.

If the complex has a stability constant greater than that of aquo or acetato complex, the reaction rate can be expected to be altered. In the case of 2-propanol, the oxidation product acetone may not form a stable complex with the intermediate oxidation states of chromium; it is possible that resonance in the dipyridyl system stabilises the transition states during reaction and this may account for the observed acceleration. Further, any addition of ligands which can decrease the $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ due to the formation of stable complex in the lower oxidation states, should accelerate the reaction.

The final solution has a dark pink colour in presence of 2,2'-dipyridyl. This is quite possible if Cr^{IV} changes by two-electron transfer to Cr^{II} which forms a complex with dipyridyl; the final complex may get oxidised by air or solvent to Cr^{III} complex. Hence in presence of 2,2'-dipyridyl, the oxidation of 2-propanol by CrO_3 is enhanced.

Effect of 1,10-phenanthroline: The added 1,10-phenanthroline affects the rate oxidation of 2-propanol as 2,2'-dipyridyl. The observed rate constants are given in Table 2 and the correlation plot of k_{obs} vs [1,10-phen] (Fig. 2c) shows a straight line. The final pink coloured product shows λ_{max} at 345 nm.

The final product of chromic acid oxidation of benzaldehyde in presence of 1,10-phenanthroline exhibits a broad band in the region 545–573 nm⁶. The mechanism of acceleration of rate is similar to that of 2,2'-dipyridyl system, this is as expected because dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline are basically similar ligands even though in the case of the latter one would expect a rigid structure. Thus the rate acceleration reveals the stabilisation of Cr^{IV} to Cr^{II} by the formation of complex with Cr^{II} , then this gets oxidised to Cr^{III} complex. During complexation, the Cr^{IV} takes two electrons from 2-propanol.

Conclusion:

The results indicate that the oxidising capacity of Cr^{VI} towards 2-propanol is retarded by added metal ions and influenced by the complexing ligands.

Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} sulphates decrease the rate constants which is highly pronounced at lower concentration and less pronounced at higher concentration of the metal ions. This may be due to equilibrium effect of the chromium species and the added metal ions and also competitive oxidation with Cr^{IV} . Fe^{II} sulphate decreases the rate constant to the maximum extent, because Fe^{II} itself can react with Cr^{VI} forming lower valent chromium species; such species may be less effective compared to Cr^{VI} in oxidising the alcohol. The added Co^{II} has no effect in this case.

The added ligands influenced the oxidation. This must be due to the complexing of not only Cr^{VI} but also lower valent chromium ions. This could be due to the formation of Cr^{IV} -ligand complex or Cr^{V} -ligand complex. Probably, electron abstraction from the substrate is facilitated by the complexed chromium species to form lower stable Cr^{III} complex. However, all the ligands do not appear to have the same capacity for increasing the oxidising ability of Cr^{IV} . The observed order is 2,2'-dipyridyl > 1,10-phenanthroline > EDTA.

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